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Rethinking Digital and Sensory Marketing in Globalizing Contexts of Political Economy: Revisiting ICT Consumer Cultures in the Symbolism and Dynamism of Postmodern Spaces

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Abstract

Digital and sensory marketing is often presented as an essentialism in itself with the potential to construct results in global consumption culture. However, this paper argues that this model of marketing is very complex because it is embedded in the dynamics of history and symbolism. Digital and sensory marketing is not constructed in a vacuum, but by generations of people who challenge orthodox views of consumption and forge their own idiosyncratic visions of marketing, which the business and corporate world soon adopt. Products and services do not have inherent properties of their own but rather draw their signification from consumption culture. The generations that drive consumption have their own attitudes and sense of self-fulfillment that eventually determine the branding experience. ICTs have a critical role to play in moulding this changing culture.

However, there are certain risks that the shifts in the value of global consumption culture may bring, particularly when it comes to new ethical questions such as how to control privacy, intrusion and the utilization of big data.

Keywords

Digital and sensory marketing, interactive contexts, generational consumer cultures, historicism, dynamism and symbolism, new ethical questions, privacy, intrusive and big data analytics issues, ICTs, value creation and individual self-fulfillment

Introduction

This paper is premised on the hypothesis that the globalizing environment of the political economy intersects with digital technology and sensory marketing in ways that are ‘literary’, discursive and very complex. This *lieux* of the intersection has the potential to construct new consumption behaviours, values and patterns to a point where they are determining a new consumption and consumer culture. To speak of digital and sensory marketing, is to talk of a globalizing consumer culture where different products, activities, brands and places are constantly being purchased and consumed in ways that are highly individualized and on the basis that is very personalized. In this critical, literary and discursive context, brands and products have new meanings for a person’s life. The symbolic content of different services, products, and goods, which is vital to a brand’s experience during consumption, is refilled by the hopes, dreams and experiences of the consumer that fuel the purchasing decision. The consumer is the site of the interface between the market and culture. The individual’s experience, self-fulfillment and image-building stress upon the emotional component, which is distinct from the strictly rational or functional basis of a brand or commodity experience.

There is now a shift to a cultural epoch displaying values that are typical for the demands of the X, Y and Z generations. This cultural shift is now impacting digital marketing and consumption and this is

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leading to breakthroughs in digital technology and social media. This impact is also creating significant exchanges in information and communication between businesses and consumers and between consumers themselves. As a result of this interstitial process, digital marketing has now coalesced with a global culture with its own products, brands, goods, places and activities. In the interstitial site, brand experience is both content and symbol; consequently, consumption is both real self-images of experience and the fiction of experience. Through symbolic content, it is possible to create and find meaning in the lives of people as Fromm (1976) enlightens us [1].

However, these digital and sensory possibilities of consumption and marketing are often represented as though they were disembedded from the globalizing and interactive environment of the political economy. It is, therefore, necessary to investigate this critical environment so that we can be empowered to understand and minimize some of the possible risks that the possibilities entail in the future.

Current scholarship on digital and sensory marketing

Current scholarship on digital and sensory marketing tends to lay stress on the surface issues as though this type of marketing functions in a historical, social and psychological vacuum. For example, Hennigs, Wiedmann, and Klarmann (2012) [2] have argued that luxury goods are purchased chiefly for what they symbolize and as a result of the emergence of multi-sensory and experiential marketing methods. They advise that it is necessary for luxury managers to construct a prestigious environment both online and offline. Nevertheless, in the ubiquity of the virtual environment in which counterfeit luxury goods are nearby, the issue is: what is the best method that can give a balance between high class and mass class? Owing to the global desire for luxury products in the new epoch of “luxurification of society” and “democratization of luxury,” luxury brands are confronted with the challenge of employing strategies of mass marketing and, at the same time, stressing upon the exclusive dimensions of their products. As a result, we should comprehend the rules and behavioural patterns within the digital marketplace. Luxury managers are still hesitant to attempt innovative digital strategies. As a democratic medium, the digital environment circulates opinions, videos and images irrespective of brand ownership, thereby making it possible to maintain exclusive fidelity around a luxury brand. This paper asks how luxury brands, considered as prestigious, and encompassing many psychological and physical values, can be managed in the digital age that has found a balance between ubiquity and exclusivity, mass class and high class.

Raising definitional issues, Hultén, Bertil, Niklas Broweus, and Marcus Van Dijk, ask "What is sensory marketing?" in a chapter that signifies sensory marketing both in theory and practice [3]. The chapter discusses what a sensory marketing framework is and compares it with relationships and mass marketing. It suggests certain sensorial strategies that stress the human senses as the focus of a company's sensory marketing and it points out the importance of the brand, the logic of experience in sensory marketing and the human senses. Krishna, Aradhna (2012) [4] define “sensory marketing” as marketing that commits consumers' senses and affects their behavior, perception and judgment. From a perspective of management, sensory marketing constructs subconscious triggers that mark consumer perceptions of abstract notions (for example, its quality, sophistication, etc.) of the product. Given the range of explicit marketing calls made to consumers on an everyday basis, subconscious triggers that speak to the basic senses can be effective in engaging consumers. As well, these sensory triggers can cause consumers to self-generate brand attributes that are desirable, rather than triggers that are verbally provided to the advertiser. The comprehension of sensory triggers suggests an understanding of sensation and perception as it applies to consumer behaviour. This article is an overview of investigations on sensory perception. It suggests areas where minimal investigations have been carried out so that others papers can make a significant difference and trigger new research. It is evident from the paper that there is still a need for further research in sensory marketing.

Petit, Olivia, et al. (2015) [5] reports about a workshop that had as objective to augment

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consciousness about the various ways in which new technologies (e.g., neuro-imaging technologies, virtual reality, social media, etc.) can be deployed as input to develop multisensory experiences to ameliorate consumer fulfillment. Consumers experience products and services through their senses such as via smell, taste, sight, hearing, and touch. The multisensory content of those products and services can impact people's purchase intentions, attitudes and consumption. Today, customers experiment the world via new technologies by sharing their sentiments through social media, or by setting up an avatar in a virtual world. The problem for marketing is in the domain of monitoring new technologies, comprehending customer sensory experiences and creating innovative actions capable of ameliorating , these experiences. After defining sensory marketing and the role of multisensory processes, it addresses the potential to understand the customer via neuroimaging technologies and social media. Lastly, it presents certain technologies to enrich the sensory experiences of customers.

Hultén (2011) [6] writes about the hypothesis of multi-sensory brand-experience by arguing that companies should apply three explanatory levels and sensorial strategies within an SM model. It empowers companies through sensors, sensations, and sensory expressions to position and differentiates a brand in the human mind as an image. The findings proffer extra insights to managers on the idea of multi-sensory brand-experience. This investigation opens up ways for managers to spot out emotional/psychological linkages in differentiating, positioning and distinguishing a brand as an image in the human mind. The main achievement of this research resides in developing the hypothesis of multi-sensory brand-experience within an SM model. It fills a principal gap in the marketing literature and research by emphasizing on the necessity to revisit classical marketing models.

This paper proposes, therefore, to excavate into the deeper sociological currents that constructed digital and sensory marketing in the past and in the present. It is suggested that this research will enable us to be apt to tackle certain critical issues that will confront this model of marketing in the future.

Methods and materials

This paper draws from the new historicist marketing paradigm developed by Achrol and Kotler (2012) [7], and Achrol and Kotler (1999) [8]. according to which the creating and delivering of value via customer relationships is now replacing the classical focus on the economic exchange paradigm.

The paper also draws from the postmodern paradigm which is based on the assumption that consumption does not occur simply as a result of material values but more critically because goods and services consumed have symbolic content. Thus, as opposed to the consumption of a tangible good or service, the foundation for consumption can also be experience-based. Seen from this light, consumption plays a critical role in determining how people live their lives and it also contributes to different brand experiences. Consumption contributes to the creation of meaning, can be perceived as a process of existential choice and is increasingly connected to the need for individualization and higher self-fulfilment as Elliott (1997) points out [9]. As a result, *purchase behaviour* was created founded on the premise of self-image creation and the experiences of the self.

There has been a shift from media information and influence, as in the past years of media advertisement and television commercials when people were persuaded to purchase products and services offered, to creation of brand inspiration and commitment, as in recent years when the younger generations have been establishing an emotional relationship as the foundation for building a customer relationship. With digital technology, any customer, whether real or virtual, can now create new sensory experiences at any time of the day, the week or the year. The cyberspatialisation of products and services means that brands, as consumer products and services, drift from the earlier conception as merely exchange products to a new notion of products as items to talk and think with as Fiske (1989) enlighten us [10]. Individuals create

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images or self-images through branding. A symbolic society is now constructed where symbolic characters create, communicate and maintain meaning and identity in marketing and consumption.

The historicity of consumerism

Digital/sensory marketing cannot be completely understood without its critical component, namely, the historicity of consumerism. This process was triggered off when local production of goods shifted grounds to the factory and their local identities got lost particularly when there was no packaging logo or name specifying their origins. The challenge that emerged for industrialists was how to construct confidence in a product or service that was not created locally because consumers were not notified of their existence. Consequently, industrialists attempted to persuade the market that they could have confidence in the product created at the national level in just the same way as they had confidence in local products. From here, the idea came up that a brand can be introduced for a product in order to augment the familiarity of the consumer with it. In the USA, a number of companies like Coca-Cola, Quaker Oats, and Campbell Soup. James Walter Thompson created an advertisement by 1900 explaining brand advertising and this then triggered the earliest start of what is referred to today as brand culture of marketing [11], [12], [13],[14],[15],[16],[17],[18]. In the following several years, this culture developed into the use of mascots, slogans and jingles on radio and eventually on television. From the 1940s/1950s, manufacturers started to think about the psychological, anthropological and social relationships that consumers developed with their brands. This was the starting point from which manufacturers began to learn about examples of concepts like youthful, fun and luxurious, in the construction of brand identity and personality. The construction of the brand is founded on the presumption that the consumer purchases a brand and not a product or service.

A brand then became the identity of a product, service, business and took the form of a symbol, name, colour, shape or character. It emerged as an attempt to create a link between the personality of a brand and the real product or service, as seen by the target audience. Because a brand name was easier to remember, it became possible to associate it with a trend, a positive connotation, a joyous event, a national hero, a rock star and so forth. The brand identity was built on the associations that businesses created and on how the target audience was supposed to perceive them. As a result, a brand's identity was designed to fit into both the functional and symbolic needs of the consumer. Consumers then comprehended brand identity in terms of what practical needs and problems it was able to solve such as the creation of social identification and development of self-image. Functionalism and symbolism then took separate directions in the consciousness of the consumer and the associations were sometimes emotional or physical. Harley-Davidson motorcycles often advertise that their motorcycle does not just function as a means of transport but is also a lifestyle experience, and a mode of expression of what one is. A number of human characteristics were used to define a brand's personality and this created an opportunity for a brand to be associated with the psychology of a consumer in terms of fantasy, attitudes, visions, thoughts, feelings and in terms of self-expression which is a symbolic function. Consumers ascribed human characteristics to brands so that they can think of them as celebrities, heroes, persons with special qualities, etc. The further implication was that a strong brand personality would augment the loyalty and trust of consumers. Relationship marketing emerged from here because of the interaction between a company and a consumer was naturalized as a long-term relationship. The relationship-oriented hypothesis developed by Charles Fourier (Korac-Kakabadse, Korac-Kakabadse, and Myers 1998) [19] signified a brand in terms of enthusiasm, activity, bonding, togetherness, commitment, intimacy, emotion and mental images of wellness. As the years went by, there was a

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significant shift from an emphasis on the product to emphasis on brand emotion. So, what connected customers and brands was no longer just product or service but the emotional experience of purchasing, as Brembeck and Ekstrom (2004) have elucidated [20]. This marked a moment of experience-oriented consumption when non-functional and symbolic and contextual aspects of the brand experience were more critical than ever before in determining product or service experience. Brand emotion and experience is a highly subjective behavioural reaction of the consumer coming from their internal senses and supported by cognition, and by the way, a brand is designed, packaged, identified, and communicated in a particular environment (Brakus et al. 2009: 59) [21]. When consumers look for a brand, they seek stimuli at various intellectual, behavioural, sensory and emotional levels. Advertising is one of the forms of stimuli. When a brand is in an experience-oriented context, it is more advantaged than one in a functional context.

The starting point where brand experience exists is where the customer comes into contact with the brand. If the effect from the contact is positive on the consumer's loyalty, associations and satisfaction, they may seek additional stimulus to their bodies and souls. In this way, consumers strengthen brand experience when they have a positive self-image. Brand image is a mental picture of a brand that consumers have depending on their own perceptions, feelings, thoughts and experiences of it in reality (Gronroos 2008) [22]. This strengthens brand awareness in consumers, so they remembered it and were able to associate it with a jingle, a name, a logo, etc. Consumer-based brand equity has been an outcome from this historicity that elucidates how consumers relate to, perceive and experience a brand. We talk of consumer-based brand equity when a brand has become so familiar that consumers have developed unique and strong associations with it. Consequently, a brand developed its own personality, relationship and experience that laid the foundation for its equity. This historicity constructed the phenomenon today of consumer marketing that takes multiple forms, such as relationship marketing, consumer behaviour, service logic, branding, mass marketing, etc. In this development, concepts like relationship, interactivity and attitudes stand out.

Symbolism in a consumer society

The global consumer society has now become a symbolic order with varied kinds of brands signifying a bridge or a link to the symbolic universe marked by experiences that an individual's consumption practices generate. The activities that generate experiences such as a meal in a restaurant, the purchase of a service or a product, a visit to a shopping center, etc., are more important than the product or service itself. Thus, the total experience, that is, the emotional and functional factors, are more critical for the brand itself. For example, Swedish consumers prefer to spend their revenue on various goods and services with the purpose of obtaining particular types of experiences. When in an enquiry, the consulting firm *Kairos Future* interrogated 2200 Swedes about their consumption habits in 2013, it was discovered that they spent one quarter of their monthly revenue, namely, 4500 SEK, to consume *pleasure*. They spent their income on food, clothing, travel and restaurant services but also spent their money on concerts, books, movies, and visits to theatrical shows (Jensen 1999:3) [23]. A major lesson from the study was that consumers expect to find aspects of entertainment in any activity of consumption and the expectation was that it should be enjoyable and fun. In any experience of consumption, consumers in all states and nations are in quest of an interesting life to sense up; they want to be entertained, explore new experiences of life and witness new places, and they wish to learn in an enjoyable way. They want to experience values that exist beyond products and services. There are *products and services* for marketing and there are also *experiences* of products and services. Today's customers and consumers are reaching out to achieve the

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ultimate goal of experiencing consumption. In this way, products and services become simply artifacts around which experience is created for individuals and persons. Experiences are created not only from commodities but also from activities concerned with tourism, digital technology, culture, smartphones, internet services, websites and so forth. The experience created is coming from the individual consumer himself/herself. They may also create an experience in association with other consumers and the experience they create becomes an *extension* of the identities of products and services being marketed.

Contemporary global culture is now being increasingly fragmented because of the knowledge of the world which is founded on the real and the symbolic. As a result, social movements define themselves not in relation to capitalism, and social class as in modern industrial societies, but rather in terms of issues and agendas based on similarities of views on questions such as peace, attitudes to animals, religion, weapons of mass destruction, gender, senior citizens and so forth. As a result of the increase in the number of these groups or *multiversum*, a diversification of opinions on various questions like sexual orientation, the environment, individualism and green spaces has emerged. In the past, it was common to identify what is good or bad about the political economy; today, all of that has changed as an individual live their everyday lives as they desire. Contemporary society is full of paradoxes and contrasts because the ‘absolute truth’ is no longer foisted upon individuals as before. With the emerging culture of diversification and difference, the individual is now seen as a fragmented ‘object’ that needs to be inputted into the neoliberal free market through ICTs and social media. That postmodern individual does not have a persistent, determined and coherent identity and this is explainable by the fact that the everyday conditions of life, work, politics, science, are constantly changing. Consequently, the digital market responded by employing the strategy of fragmentation in order to customize solutions for particularly targeted groups and meet the needs of individuals with different lifestyles and identities of consumption. Like the Belgian Crock’In chain, there has been a transition from mass marketing and production as in a modern industrial society where the individual was an ‘object’ to a new globalized culture where the individual is a ‘subject’ with fragmented identity formations. The Belgian Crock’In chain is a brand that prides itself in the marketing of high quality foods. It states in its adverts that it does not deal with mass produced food items like salads, sandwiches, soup and cakes from industrial complexes but takes its time to prepare its own food as though it was food stewed at the individual’s home.

The dynamism of global and digitized marketing

There is marketing, on the one hand, and there is marketing *dynamism*, on the other hand. Market *dynamism* is contingent upon the creation of this symbolism through new innovations, new knowledge content, new ideas and new services. The transition from mass production and marketing to the customization of products/services and individualization of marketing was motivated by this new emphasis on brand experience than on just the product or service in the global marketing context. What accounted for the dynamism of global marketing have been the ICTs and the shift in cultural value. ICTs and the shift in cultural value acted in symbiosis to construct new consumption patterns, behaviours and values. These patterns, behaviours and values necessitated the development of new communication strategies for dialogue and creation of value in order to boost consumer marketing. Consequently, modern industrial society came under enormous pressure to adopt new cultural values in consumption. The different generations (X, Y, Z) impacted new forms of comprehension of consumption and marketing and ICTs and social media played new roles in the intersection of consumption and companies and in the interface of consumers themselves. Brand experience in the global and digitized marketing environment was one where products, services,

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brands, places, and activities are subjected to a new consumerist culture in ways that are highly sensitive to the need for personalization and individualization. There was a re-focusing from products to the significance of brands in the life of a consumer, and the effects of such concentrations on the meanings of consumer activities. Thus, there was a shift from an emphasis on products and services in the past to stress on the symbolism of brands, the hopes, dreams and experiences of consumers that steer their buying decisions in the consumption culture. Unlike in the past, when consumption and the marketing technologies were seen as separate entities, in the global consumption culture, both entities are being perceived as one entity supporting each other and are being actively and intimately associated with the quests for self-fulfilment, image construction and experiences of individual consumers. There was a shift from the strict rationalist and functional basis to an emotional, symbolic and sentimentalist foundation of marketing and consumption.

The symbolism of consumption in a brand's content is not static either. It is very dynamic because it is founded not only on real self-images but also on fictitious experiences. In this way, the meaning was constructed and identified in the lives of consumers (Fromm 1976) [1]. As a result of this dynamism, television and advertising commercials became more creative, inspirational and pleasurable. The old function of the platforms consisting of merely influencing and informing consumers to purchase products and services started to wane and were replaced by the emotionizing and sentimentalizing of relationships as a basis for constructing inspiration and commitment from a customer to a product, service or brand. Both virtual and real consumers constructed new sensory experiences for a whole day, week or month for their own enjoyment and consumption. Products, services and brands shifted from being merely entities of exchange use and could now assume new personalities of their own as consumers were able to converse and think with them (Fiske 1989) [10]. A symbolic society was created in which the self-image of the consumer as product or service coalesced and characters symbolically created, maintained and communicated social meaning and identity in marketing and consumption. Brands began to incarnate a link connecting the symbolic society and the experiences of the individual consumer. What really mattered was not so much the functions of the product or service, but rather the emotion they inspired. With new content, new innovations and new services, the conditions were ripe for a new dynamic digitized market in the global cultural arena. What was critical was not the commodity *per se* but the experience of activities around the commodity such as in the website, tourism, mobile phones, culture and internet services. Individual consumers became creators of experience and products and services became antecedent to consumer experiences.

The transition that took place from mass production and marketing to the customization of products and services and the individualization of consumption experiences has been explained in terms of classical sociological concepts. These concepts proffer the understanding that states and nations all over the world witnessed a social change in terms of the transition from first to second and then to third waves. The first wave of agricultural society terminated in mid-1800 when the Industrial Revolution started in earnest in England as a result of various intellectual, social, economic, cultural and political changes. This transition, which was also called the modernist project, the Enlightenment or the great transformation (Polanyi 1973) was made possible because new forms of social processing, socializing and social life were adopted [24]. The second wave of industrial modernization was spurred by new techniques and methods of manufacturing and food production, the factory system with its division of labour, and this was represented as the progress of capitalism over manual agriculture. This new age of industrial society was marked by a shift in attitudes

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from conservatism to rationalism in development of the economy, the creation of new ideas, institutions and companies, the development of new technologies of leadership and of products, and the increase in the production of goods and professionalized services for increased profitability. The second wave ended in the mid-1970s and the third wave or postmodern stage started off in the last decades of the *fin de siècle*. This wave has been marked by cultural value shifts in which old-established understandings about religion, politics, business, the economy, family and social advertisement were challenged and re-assessed (Inglehart 1997) [25].

However, these sociological concepts that are used to explain the three waves of change processes from pre-modernization to modernization and postmodernization are inadequate to articulate the key issues in cultural value systems and interpret the problematic of change that is linked to economic development. Postmodernism is an adequate temporal framework that explicates how the social change took place from the 1980s onward. One of the greatest changes was the globalization of capitalism in terms of physical geography and the geographies of labour. For example, industries outsourced production to Third World nation states and, as a result, traditional modes of production and manual labour disintegrated in the west. The service industry increased to replace manufacturing. As a result, a number of concepts such as disorganized capitalism, post-Fordism and flexible capital growth were devised and employed to explicate this new form of a globalized society. As capital mobility and financial markets globalized and job investments in the electronics, motor car and fashion industries re-located to Third World nation states, particularly, to Southeast Asia and Africa, knowledge and service production came to replace classical industrial production, thereby placing new constraints on economic mobility, flexibility and adjustments.

The continuum intersecting Fordism and post-Fordism is a model with illustrative power capable of efficiently explicating shifts in the assembly line of the 1920s to the 1970s introduced by the US car manufacturer Gerard Ford. The Fordist side of the continuum suggests that production was a question of mass production of cars for a mass market of consumers, marked by full employment, welfare and high living standards. But with the oil crisis of the 1970s and the increasing competition of the global economies, new ideas about management, business, new technologies and social life emerged that could only be explicated by the post-Fordism paradigm of the continuum. With new terms like flexible company, flexible specialization and flexible economic growth, it was then possible to efficiently explain the shift from Fordism to post-Fordism. The notion of flexible economic growth articulated the shift from an emphasis on production and consumption of products and services to an increasing stress on knowledge and information which were now seen to be more important. The idea of mass production via market segmentation was replaced mass customization also referred to as mass individualization. This simply signified that there was now closer contact between customers and the industry sector thanks to the power of ICTs, flexible manufacturing systems and automation. As a result, the US manufacturer of computers, Dell, used pre-determined variants for the customer such as type of software, processor, screen dimension, laptop or desktop, etc. to construct and equip personal computers. ICTs then became the vital force that drove the globalization of products, services, brands and ideas for the new contemporary economy.

Postmodernization impacted heavily on consumption and marketing by creating new family relationships through digital forums, new consumption patterns and new values. From the 1990s, well-being and quality of life became more important than products, services and brands (Inglehart 1997) [25] as needs, accomplishments and experiences of individuals became the focus of consumer interest. A distinctive culture emerged where consumers no longer had any particular or pre-determined values because of socio-

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economic dynamism in everyday life, politics, the workplace, etc. during these decades. The individual endowed himself with a greater role to play over social and economic practices of collective responsibility in the past. When agricultural society transited to modern society, the popular view at the time was that the increase in collective responsibility, social mobility and social solidarity would occasion economic growth and social prosperity. In modern society, innovation, economic success, hard work and individualism were prioritized over religious norms, inherited status and ‘qualities one was born with.’ Technological and management developments facilitated economic growth in modern industrialized society. The centralization of bureaucracy and assembly lines soon gave way to trade unions and to individual capital growth.

Today, there is a questioning of modern industrial society in terms of its materialist values such as the bureaucratic state and the assembly line with workers routinized like ‘machines’ subjected to standardized procedures. They challenged the depersonalization and dehumanization that occasioned costs such as poor quality of life and ill-health as preconditions for economic growth. In the post-materialist society of today, values such as quality of life and self-fulfillment are prioritized over materialist considerations. The drive has been more toward freedom of speech, expression of personal opinion on government, the spread of ideas more than monetary considerations, and the personalization of society as opposed to the maintenance of order, stability of economic growth, the fight against crime and rising prices, the maintenance of strong defence forces, and so forth (Inglehart 1990) [26]. With rising living standards in the 1950s to the 1970s, there was a value shift from materialism to quality of life with the formation of political and social movements such as Friends of the Earth, environmental movements and Greenpeace. Greenpeace and numerous environmental movements have been engaged in influencing various practices in digital marketing and consumption. The decades from 1886 to 1945 were marked chiefly by the quest for economic success. Today, youths think of themselves much more in hedonistic than in materialistic terms, much more in the light of the quality of life and pampering of the self than in terms of collective responsibility, traditional norms and bearing the costs of bureaucratic efficiency (Wilkinson and Mulgan 1995) [27]. The ‘me-society’ based on self-promotion is gradually being replaced by the ‘I-society’ based on self-fulfillment (Howard and Mason 2001) [28]. The emphasis now is on identity, individuality, security for survivability and self-assertion than on money, work, affluence and social effectivity. Individualization and self-assertion have now become a vital prerequisite for digital marketing, sensitivity and consumption.

Discussion

It is evident from these analyses that contrary to orthodox thinking, digital and sensory marketing does not take place in a social vacuum, but rather, it is constructed by different interactive contexts of historicism, symbolism and dynamism in consumer culture. Digital and sensory marketing are affected both indirectly and directly by the value system and the culture that prevails in a given society. In order to deeply understand digital and sensory marketing, we need to comprehend how shifts in cultural value are perceived in areas like knowledge, everyday life experiences and society’s culture. One of the markers of global society’s culture today is the disordering of time. This signifies that we live in a global world of culture which enables individuals to create new experiences, consider diverse perspectives and craft out new identities for themselves. Digital technology fits well in this culture as an enabler because any customer can consume a product or service at any place or time in accordance with his desires. In order to have a deep reading of why digital and sensory marketing is so successful today, we need to understand that a major feature of today’s culture is that there is increasing focus on the design, experience and style of products,

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services and brands as opposed to the past when the concentration was on content and substance. In the past, there was a clear distinction between ‘reality’ and ‘fiction’; today, that distinction is increasingly unclear because there is a crafty mixture of the visual, the fictional, humour and reality to create postmodern effects in television commercials, digital marketing and advertising and so on. High art popular forms of art are now undistinguishable and there is a greater tendency to exercise tolerance toward social heterogeneity, ideas and beliefs as legitimate. Today’s generation is more skeptical toward all forms of metanarratives that overwhelm and totalize experience.

The digital marketing environment is thus a response to various cultural values that deal with the demographics of behavior, knowledge and facts, everyday life, diversity, data, fragmentation of niche areas, the learning economy and people (Hulten et al. 2009) [29]. The shift from tangible assets like capital, land and labour to intangible ones like brands and patents had a role to play in the evolving of the digital market. Complexity and diversity from knowledge permeated the sensory market environment. Therefore, it became difficult for businesses and the corporate world to reach out and target such an environment of complexity and diversity. The only option left was for the marketing environment to deploy digitalization to capture the very abstract values in the new intellectual thinking, and the individual experiences and subjective feelings. The individual’s real world that had to be captured was based on the symbolic world that he created and was abstract. The knowledge of social reality in this age of globalization is not a collective, homogeneous reality but an individualized, personalized and relativised one related to the time and place where it is found. This poststructuralist epoch could only be portrayed in a complex technology like ICTs and social media with various options for the script, sound, video, animation, infographics, etc. knowledge is not absolute but rather relative and dependent upon the social environment and time that created it. From this light, knowledge cannot be represented as true but as contingent upon its creators.

In order to meet individual needs of lifestyle and identity as far as consumption is concerned, the strategy today is to customize solutions, make adjustments in the targeting of groups and enforce market fragmentation. In this way, the Belgian Crock’In chain has become a brand linked to the symbolic world of individuals who insist on having their food prepared in a particularly traditional way with freshness. The Ikea effect (Norton, Morton and Ariely 2012) [30] as well has been made possible and necessary by these dynamics, which start from the premise that a product created by an individual is given greater value than that produced by other people. Like furniture that is purchased at Ikea, consumers give more value to furniture they themselves designed and produced. Businesses are now trying to employ various strategies to construct an Ikea effect for their brands so that individual customers can exercise effective control over product creation and, in this way, contribute to the identity formation and experience of consumers. Websites customize various products in such a way that their respective designs, prices, etc. can be selected by customers according to their desire. Customization augments individual involvement and the time that is spent with a selection of features of a product or service is important because it augments the consumer’s freedom of choice and his Ikea effect. Products and services do not only have a functional role, but they also have symbolic meanings that are socially innovative. The basic functions of a product or service are connected to their symbolic meanings which are created and shaped by institutions, organizations, human beings and aesthetics. In this postmodern epoch, the consumption of a product or a service is increasingly about self-image and social spectacle than about material objectivism (Firat and Venkatesh 1995: 250) [31]. So, contemporary society is characterized by spectacularity, in the sense that products and services are inscribed in meanings that create experiences which may be real or fictional for the consumer.

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With the symbolic meanings of commodities in focus, the chief role of consumption and digital marketing is to contribute to the construction of the consumer's self-fulfillment by creating his identity through symbols, culture, aesthetics, language productivity and everyday life events. In the process of attaining self-fulfillment, the individual consumer is represented as a sovereign and rational figure, who is striving to optimize the value of his life through personalization of his choices in the universe of capitalist products and services (Du Gray et al. 1997) [32]. Consumption is not a given any longer, but an assumption posited according to which consumers themselves engender self-images, images and identities through products and services in order to fulfill their hopes, dreams and wishes. In the universe of globalization, individual consumers experiment with various roles, identities and self-images which, themselves, are susceptible to alternative images and identities. With fragmentation, life-style stories are narrated online through games, movies, e-books and through real-life experiences. Thus, through hyper-reality (Kellner 1995) [33], a digital world of imagination and fantasy is created in which the individual consumer explores his identity by fusing the everyday life and the unreal life experiences. Products, services and any kinds of commodities have embedded in them cultural and social traits that, in turn, incarnate meanings capable of creating new identities, values, attitudes and symbols by while the younger generations live. The different generations (X, Y, Z) are impacting on the consumption and marketing culture in ways that create mobility. Mobility is taking multiple forms such as displacements of labour, travel, multiculturalism and development of ICT skills for constructing experiences of social change.

These generations construct new views on issues like family life, As skilled communicators or novices in the deployment of digital technologies, they are able to use their independence of mind to challenge old practices, traditions and customs whether in consumption and/or in everyday life experiences. For example, for the old generation, work means 'loyalty'; for the younger generation that signification of work has shifted to 'contract' and is now taking other meanings such as working in more than one job place, working for several hours across many jobs, resigning from one job to take on another more lucrative or more socially fulfilling one, etc. The old concept of work as a lifetime experience followed by retirement is falling out of favour with the younger generations in the globalization context. The 'net generation' or Generation Y, born between 1977 and 1997, are considered as professionals who have a natural inclination to deploy ICTs to narrate their everyday lives. The 'MeWe' Generation of the 1980s is energetic, progressive and ambitious and shows disrespect for norms, codes of conduct, authority, hierarchy and morality (Parment 2008) [34]. They brand on their own, they are open-minded to multiculturalism and internationalism. This explains why the Sweden of the 1980s was marked by ethnic and cultural diversity (Ibid). They are globetrotters with much knowledge about the world and believe that work is not simply about money-making, but it is more importantly about fun and personal development.

The Generation Next or the Generation Z born from 1998 are techno-savvy and insist not only on collecting information but also on understanding how to understand, investigate and assess information (Dillon 2007) [35]. Because they spend more time watching television and on the internet, they are more informed in influencing parental choice on products, brands and services like cars, phones, shoes, clothes, computers, etc. They are integrators of multicultural values, and digital technology is a force for change in consumption and marketing. As an instrument for self-fulfillment and individualization, ICTs (websites, blogs, social media, etc.) are employed to implement change in consumption and marketing. They are sensitive to concepts like choice, emotional connection, curiosity, interest, value and entertainment. Because the children of this generation have a potent impact on what products and services are bought and

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used, it is accurate to state that younger children are driving consumption in all areas of everyday life, education, healthcare, sports, entertainment, work and communication. Movie and television characters like James Bond are used to construct a connection between the world of fiction and the world of reality, and by so doing, the young generation creates an imagined identity (Atkinson 2005) [36] about masculinity and the challenges of the current world. As a result, in Sweden, new sales records were set in 2014 in the sector of e-commerce; other types of products in leisure, sports, children's toys, electronics, construction of homes increased by twenty to forty percent (Ibid). in this case, 70% of consumers bought their products online and 10% of them purchased their products via the phone (Ibid).

Thanks to *showrooming*, consumers search for a product in a storeroom and purchase it on a later date. With WiFi networks, consumers can search for products consumers can now obtain digital coupons directly in their phones through location-based marketing which is activated when the customer is a hundred meters away from a store. Consumers can also use QR codes to purchase milk, ketchup, etc. in a virtual store. New digital networks and forums are created nowadays to influence marketing and consumption (Kozinets et al. 2008, Godin 1999) [37]. With permission marketing, it is now possible to for businesses and consumers to participate in dialogue through interactive communication

Concluding remarks

This paper has shown that digital and sensory marketing does not function in a vacuum, but is constructed by a complex interactive environment that is historically complex, dynamic and symbolic. To understand what digital and sensory marketing are all about, we must understand this historical, dynamic and symbolic environment. It is an environment that is offering unlimited opportunities for interactivity and networking between businesses and consumers, businesses and individuals, individuals and individuals, etc. ICTs are challenging the mode of communication in industrial society thanks to blogs, social networking and social media. Consumers explore the market in their blogs while companies explore their brands on their websites. ICTs can now expand the possibilities of interactivity because, unlike other media like newspapers, radio and television, because they offer not only textual but also audio and visual mediums of communication. This two-way mode of communication has the potential to enrich marketing and consumption because it integrates rational, symbolic and emotional dimensions of interaction. ICTs are being used not only by businesses but also by politicians to update their constituencies on the latest political issues by celebrities such as rockstars, sports stars, etc. The use of digital technologies whether as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Myspace or YouTube, is now shifting power from manufacturers of products and services to consumers. Producers can no longer influence consumers; instead, consumers have the power to determine how communication between producers and customers will take place. This means that individual customers have the power to decide which brands will be consumed and which will not in order to build self-image and self-fulfillment. In this two-way traffic, companies can use digital technology to target particular messages for certain groups of consumers. Similarly, companies can also deploy digital technology to obtain precious information in the form of big data about the behavior and attitudes of consumers. In this way, technology can offer marvelous opportunities for business in terms of satisfying the desires of individuals and contributing to their targets for self-fulfillment.

However, despite these achievements and advantages of the digital technology in marketing and the sensory dimensions of consumption, it is important to note, as the paper points out, that these achievements and advantages did not come to us on their own terms. Rather, they came thanks to the dynamism of history

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and the shifting power of the corporate world of business that was appropriated by the investments of individuals and groups of people in the symbolic meanings of everyday experience. Consequently, changes in the global culture of consumption and marketing are inevitable, but they also come with certain ethical concerns that must be addressed. These challenges have to do with questions of privacy and the determination of what kind of data on users have to remain public in networking sites and what kind has to remain private. Facebook offers marvelous opportunities for companies to access useful business information about consumers' inefficient ways; however, the challenge is how to prevent or minimize the invasion of privacy. While interactivity is a good outcome for individuals driving the marketing and consumption process, there are risks in terms of digital addiction and there is a need to construct a safe and secure digital environment so that consumers can shop for their products and services without the threat of intrusion.

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